

Identifying the Maturity of Communication Processes in Distributed Software Development of Two Software Organizations

There isn't a specific assessment method for communication in DSD. The author concluded this fact after performing two systematic reviews in DSD literature. Within this context, the method used in this was a simplified derivation from SCAMPI [CMMI 2006] method and this research aims to assess two organizations with experience in distributed software development using the Communication Maturity Model (C2M).

C2M Assessment Method

Assessment methods define a set of activities for data retrieval and analysis, generating the current state of processes of an organization, indicating strengths, weaknesses and opportunities for improvement. The purpose of using an assessment method is the standardization of the assessment procedure, allowing the results comparison. The assessment methods related to this work are presented below.

The assessment method has its basis on SCAMPI - Standard CMMI Appraisal Method for Process Improvement (CMMI, 2006). Table I describes the four main elements of the C2M assessment method.

Table I – Main elements of the C2M assessment method.

Method element	Detail	Origin
1. Purpose	The method identifies informally the organization objectives with this attempt to perform an assessment.	SCAMPI
2. Scope	An assessment scope was discussed right before each interview between the organization's professional and the interviewer.	
3. Planning	An assessment planning was made previous to all interviews.	
4. Interviews	Interviews were used as a way for unedifying the existence of C2M practices on the assessed organization.	

Moreover, the following list of activities are proposed:

- I) To prepare the assessment – construction of interview scripts, preparation of assessment artifacts, selection of representative stakeholders and scheduling of interview sessions;
- II) To perform the assessment – interviews, interviews results analysis and adequacy of unit's maturity levels;
- III) To identify improvements – documentation of improvement suggestions.

During the interview, C2M practices used within the organizations are identified by asking direct questions about each practice implementation, and listening to all verbal evidences. The implementation level of each practice (or even its absence) is distinguished by the interviewer according to her expertise in software engineering and according to the answers given by the interviewee. The results are registered by the means of four characterization rules, detailed in Table II.

Table II – Rules for characterization of implementation degrees.

Characterization	Requirement	Percentage of implementation of related practice.
Totally implemented (T)	There is an evidence of a complete and systematic approach to the practice and its full implementation, with no relevant weaknesses.	from 85% to 100%
Largely implemented (L)	There is an evidence of a systematic approach to the practice and a significant degree of its implementation, but with weaknesses.	from 50% to 84%
Partially implemented (P)	There is some evidence of a focused approach to the practice and some degree of its implementation. There are weaknesses and some unpredicted aspects of its implementation.	from 15% to 49%
Not implemented (N)	There is little or no evidence of an implementation approach to the practice.	from 0 to 14%

The next step is to apply the characterization (described in Table I) over the data extracted from the assessment of the practices in the organizations that are selected for adherence verification. This task results in a data mapping that is used as basis to organize the research results. Table III represents an aggregation of practices on its respective maturity factors and exposes an aggregation factor which is named as adherence. It is filled according to the results that are expressed by the following formula: *adherence = (more than 50% of incidence of (“T” or “L”) practices)*. When this formula is satisfied for the characterized practices under the respective maturity factor, the organization is adherent to the factor of the C2M.

Assessment of the Organizations

The organizations evaluated in our study work in a distributed manner, i.e., projects are distributed over 2 or more locations. Table III lists the involved organizations:

Table III – Assessed organizations

Organization	Continent	DSD Dispersion Level	Years of experience	Team size	Development objectives	Organizational unit used for assessment
Org1	Americas	Global	10	About 7 members	New products and maintenance	Development project
Org2	Americas	Global	2	About 3 members	New products and maintenance	Whole organization

Findings

Table IV presents the adherence of assessed organizations to each C2M factor. The Organization Org1 is adherent to 11 maturity factors, Organization Org2 is adherent to five maturity factors. Organizations Org1, presented better adherence, possibly by the fact that these organizations have more years of experience in DSD.

Table IV – Findings assessment of the organizations

Maturity level	Maturity factor	No. of practices	Aggregated characterization (A) – The number of practices in each characterization level (columns “T”, “L”, “P”, and “N”) and the adherence value for the respective maturity factor (column “A”) will assume the “Y” and “N” values, indicating adherent and non-adherent status, respectively.									
			Organization Org1					Organization Org2				
			T	L	P	N	A	T	L	P	N	A
2	Management of cultural differences	2	0	1	1	0	N	0	1	0	1	N
	Tools to support communication	2	0	1	1	0	N	0	1	1	0	N
	IT Infrastructure	2	2	0	0	0	Y	0	0	0	2	N
	Management of geographic distance	2	1	0	0	1	N	2	0	0	0	Y
	Management of temporal distance	2	1	0	1	0	N	0	0	0	2	N
	Stakeholder’s management	2	0	2	0	0	Y	0	1	1	0	N
	Communication planning	7	6	1	0	0	Y	0	0	2	5	N
	Risk management	3	0	0	0	3	N	0	0	1	2	N
	Communication patterns and policies	1	1	0	0	0	Y	0	0	0	1	N
Requirements elicitation and specification	2	1	0	1	0	N	1	1	0	0	Y	
3	Management of cultural differences	3	0	0	1	2	N	0	0	0	3	N
	Trust development	3	0	0	2	1	N	0	0	1	2	N
	Tools to support communication	1	1	0	0	0	Y	0	1	0	0	Y
	IT Infrastructure	1	1	0	0	0	Y	0	0	1	0	N
	Management of geographic distance	2	1	0	1	0	N	1	0	0	1	N
	Management of temporal distance	2	0	1	0	1	N	0	0	0	2	N
	Stakeholder’s management	1	0	1	0	0	Y	0	0	1	0	N
	Communication planning	2	0	2	0	0	Y	0	1	0	1	N
	Risk management	1	0	0	0	1	N	0	0	0	1	N
	Communication patterns and policies	1	0	0	1	0	N	0	0	0	1	N
	Communication training	3	0	0	0	3	N	0	0	0	3	N
Configuration management	3	1	1	0	1	Y	2	0	0	1	Y	
Requirements elicitation and specification	1	0	0	0	1	N	0	0	0	1	N	
4	Stakeholder’s management	1	0	1	0	0	Y	0	1	0	0	Y
	Monitoring, measurement and analysis	3	1	1	1	0	Y	1	0	0	2	N
	Communication continuous improvement	4	0	1	2	1	N	1	0	1	2	N
	Communication training program	1	0	0	0	1	N	0	0	0	1	N

During the assessment of Organization Org1 and regarding the “trust development” factor, it was reported that in some aspects there is still unpredictability. In Organization Org2, the overall adherence was lower compared with the others; a possible explanation could be due to its size and experience, that is, the organization is small and it is in the beginning of its operation. In addition, Organization Org2 stated that it was difficult to formalize activities and general information flow. It was also highlighted that there were initiatives for achieving better approaches, but only a few communication elements were formalized. It was observed that a planning for frequent communication approaches was in use, but the time zone management was never considered among its members. Regarding the “communication planning” and “monitoring measurement and analysis” factors.

Suggestions of Improvement for the Organizations

It was identified that the two assessed organizations could not achieve adherence to any maturity level of the C2M model; however, these organizations performed adherence on many practices, i.e., they are aware of using best practices for improving its communication processes. Based on the performed assessment it was possible to report some improvement suggestions on the communicative processes of the distributed teams within these organizations (described in Table V). These suggestions were composed by a list of Maturity factors and practices that were mostly characterized with “P” (partially implemented) and “N” (not implemented) values and with non-adherent results for the same maturity factor under previous maturity levels. The results are not applicable to all software development organizations given the particularities each organization has that might affect communication. However, they provide initial insights about the validity of our proposed method. Also, concerning the organization Org2, as being a smaller company, it can benefit from the improvement suggestions as an approach for establishing a more efficient communication basis for the evolution of its processes.

Table V – Suggestions of Improvement for the Organizations

Organization	Improvement Suggestion
Org1	It is advisable to establish the Risk Management maturity factor , by performing the communication risk identification, evaluation, categorization, prioritization and all its associations with the organization's stakeholders.
	It is also advisable to improve the management of cultural differences factor , by performing the establishment of a cultural knowledge base and planning of initiatives to mitigation of occurrences caused by cultural differences.
	It is advisable to establish some communication training programs factor , mostly on preparation and deployment of training classes.
	It is advisable to focus on thrust development factor , mostly in the interchange of members between the dispersed teams of the project.
Org2	It is advisable to focus on communication planning factor , mostly on the definition of a communication strategy, confirmation of understanding of activities and a communication plan.
	It is advisable to improve the IT Infrastructure factor , mostly on definition of the infrastructure considering the team dispersion and monitoring mechanisms.

	It is advisable to establish the management of temporal distance factor , by performing the synchronization of team schedules and the planning of occurrences mitigation on this factor.
	It is also advisable to improve the management of cultural differences factor , mostly on the identification of the cultural context of each team on the project.
	It is advisable to focus on thrust development factor , mostly on collaboration and cooperation between teams.
	It is advisable to establish the risk management factor , by performing on communication risk identification, evaluation, categorization and prioritization.
	It is advisable to establish some communication training programs factor , mostly on preparation and deployment of training classes.
	It is advisable to focus on communication patterns and policies factor , mostly on establishing a communication policy.

Suggestion of Improvements for C2M

The interviews were also used for collecting improvement suggestions for the C2M model. According to Organization Org1, the understanding of the C2M practices can lead to a broader view of planning possibilities that could result in improvements. It was also declared that all C2M practices are relevant to DSD organizations. Finally, according to organization Org2, it was observed that all practices and factors of the C2M model are well organized into its maturity levels. However, it was stated that communication trainings would not always work as the best approach for sharing the communication initiatives within organizations. The overall feedback from organizations about the C2M model was positive, it was stated that the C2M will provide means for identify and think about better ways for dealing with the communication under their organizations.

Conclusion:

The assessment of the organizations described in this paper showed that specific C2M maturity factors (with their practices) need attention when the organizational goal is to be totally adherent to a specific C2M maturity level. Additionally, an assessment method can be used as a tool for single and possible subsequent verifications of the organization's current progress with the C2M model, leading to the improvement of communication in DSD organizations.

Reference

CMMI (2006). CMMI ® for Development , Version 1 . 2. n. August.